

PACIFICUS

A LITERARY MAGAZINE

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A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“SANDIGAN NG ANAK”

Sa bawat araw na ika'y nagigising,
Ang puso mo'y pilit na bumabangon,
Lumipas man ang kanyang mahal,
Pag-ibig mo sa anak ay di mawawala noon.

Sa gitna ng unos at dilim,
Ikaw ang tanglaw na di maglilim,
Tangan ang lakas ng isang ina,
Pag-asa nila sa bawat umaga.

Sa bawat luha na iyong pinigilan,
Nakatago ang tapang na di matitinag,
Ang mga anak mo'y iyong yaman,
Kahit nawala ang kanilang tatay, sa'yo sila'y sumasandal.

Ina, ikaw ang ilaw at gabay,
Tiwala nila'y nasa iyong kamay,
Sa hirap at ginhawa, ikaw ang sandigan,
Pagmamahal mo'y walang kapantay, tunay na ligaya ng tahanan.

Categories

Please **HIGHLIGHT** the category that best fits your submission:

- ◆ **Poetry**
- ◆ **Short Stories**
- ◆ **Essays**
- ◆ **Spotlight on Emerging Writers**
- ◆ **Creative Corner**
- ◆ **Others:** _____ (Please specify)

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